

Redefining Mechatronics for the future

Revision 4 volume 1

Masterclass | TT Mokgohloa
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1. INTRODUCTION

If I was to define mechatronics It's not what many think, that it is a field that combines Mechanical, Electrical and Computer engineering to develop sophisticated machines and processes.

2: Curiosity

This is a story of the remarkable progress been made by mankind. From a simple curiosity came this wonderful exploration of matter together.

The real question is where is this curiosity leading us? (The innovation and engineering curiosity)?

3: Founding of logic system

George Boole was a born Mathematician, at age 20 he formed his own school where he taught Mathematics, a subject that he actually learnt on his own. He was such a genius and discovered that his algebra could also be applied in logic.

Boole's reasoning has led to applications of which he never dreamed—for example, telephone switching and electronic computers use binary digits and logical elements that rely on Boolean logic for their design and operation. (1)

4: Rossum's Universal Robot

Ironically the word ROBOT had a completely different meaning. Coined by a Czech Artist Josef Čapek to refer to hard labour. He was an older brother to Karel Čapek, and both worked on numerous plays and art works. Around 1920s they introduced a play about a bad day at a

Mechatronics as per the evolution in history means the design, innovation of technologies and principles to optimise integrated machines, protect life and environment from preventable harms.

factory which had employed Human-like machines.

Their father was a medical doctor at a textile factory. Although Karel only acknowledged that his father had an influence in his career, it is very likely that he and his brother's plays were in some sense attempting to prevent the injuries and illnesses people sustained at their father's work. Another play by Josef is called the insects' life, was yet again the idea of a machine mimicking a living creature. (2)
(3)

This was really the early stages of thinking of machines doing complicated human tasks and the dangers of being too reliant thereof. And mostly likely had inspired some of the films that were released after that, the likes of Robocop, The Matrix and so on.

5: First Robot used in production

George Devol, was a successful man in the 60s. And had dedicated his life to being an inventor. Among his inventions was a "programmed article transfer" which he later sold to General motors to be used in a part of production process. (4)

6: "Father of the PLC"

A 36 years old Richard Morley was working on a number of engineering proposals for the firm he founded, Bedford Associates engineering consulting firm. One of these projects that was due was a Machine control for General motors.

Morley woke up the 1st of January 1968 with a hangover and a reprieve from his company. For that split second an idea dawn on him, of a system that could be a solution to all his projects. He identified that thought these projects are different, they are in fact all having the same problem. Morley then wrote a 12 page document proposing what we now call the Programmable Logic Controller. (5)

7: Birth of Mechatronics

Tetsuro Mori was employed as an engineer at Yaskawa in 1948 and became factory manager of small induction motors in 1957. The department was not performing well at the time due to the recession. The staff in this department was essentially at the verge of losing their job and Mori was haunted by this prospect.

One of his initial ideas of products was a machine called the “MO-CHIN-TROL” which means Motor machine control. He and his colleagues were attempting to integrate electric motor with mechanics and controls.

He has managed to actually save the production of small motors, also the contributing factor was that factories were starting divide the production process into automated modules. Instead of relying on one big electric motor, now more and smaller electric motor were being required.

As he proceeded to refine his system “MO-CHIN-TROL” and when he asked colleagues to adopt it for their production line and to evaluate it at an in-house exhibition, the director of marketing told him “We can go ahead with your system, but we can't call it ‘MO-CHIN-TROL’ . It

doesn't sound good and it sounds unsophisticated. Think of a cool name for it.” Then he came up with the “MECHATRONICS” from Mechanism and Electronics, and he filed it as a trademark at Yaskawa and was registered in 1971.

Originally, Mechatronics was created as a concept for new product development and as a philosophy for factory operation at Yaskawa. (6)

8: First Mechatronics qualification

The term Mechatronics entered academics in the 90s. An Austrian university was first to introduce Mechatronics degree programme in the world. (7)

9: Present day

The World Economic forum in 2020 already made a predicted that 50% of all employees will need reskilling by 2025, as adoption of technology increases, according the World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs Report (8). This reskills is already taking place, as more systems are being integrated, and software solutions advancement are being introduced. This supports the need to redefine Mechatronics and other qualifications.

Topics to be covered in mechatronics are broad. Since Mechatronics is centred around the integration of systems from various fields of engineering the topics vary a lot. From basics of Mechanics building up to complex integration automated system. The specialisation is also another important factor. There are artisans, technicians, engineers, scientists and so on. In this paper the focus is on a Mechatronics Technician. The definition of a mechatronics technician that gained most ratings is one that covered broader functions as well as the job description. Mechatronics includes mechanical, Electrical, pneumatics, electrically operated systems, programming, Robotics and development

of systems. The job of a mechatronics technician is to integrate these areas: to design, build, maintain, repair automated

equipment, program equipment controls and factory assembly lines (9)

11: Results: Qualitative Evaluation:

The qualitative assessment was conducted using a questionnaire conducted to participants face to face and telephonically. The questions assessed various topics: relevance, year of introduction, as well as levels of complexities. The participants are people mainly from Automotive, process and education industries with an array of years of experience in the field, ranging from a few years to decades.

Figure 1: Teaching methodology

Below topics are derived from my observations in different industries mainly in Process and automotive. As well as from my previous publications in the topic of Mechatronics. There are additional topics that were brought up by the people that took part in the research interviews, which I have to admit, are absolutely important to consider and are listed at the end.

Level 2 and Level 3

Figure 2: Topics by order of importance

Level 4 and Leve 5

Figure 3: Topics by order of importance

A total of 71 topics were surveyed, including theory and practical tasks. Also addressing topics in fabrication, assembly, installing, wiring, programming, commissioning, servicing, and optimisation. In the end the totals for each level were as follows:

2	3	4	5
68	122	87	79

12. Conclusion

While it is important to stay up to date in teaching mechatronics, it is equally important to be familiar with the history. Although Mechatronics was not originally founded as a field of study, but rather as a device. The motivation for this discovery is similar with the implementation in education and the industry demands. Ultimately, a mechatronics technician is distinguishable from other professions by the ability to integrate systems that were previously isolated.

70 percent of the results for teaching methodology supports “first install, service then modify”. This model has its roots in the cognitive development such as in Bloom’s taxonomy. We also observe it in the approach to Mechatronics tasks in the WorldSkills competitions. The principle is that learners are taught how to make an initial basic model, then service, maintain, repair, modify and optimise it in a progressive approach.

This approach has a Great potential to instil s sustainability culture in the participants. Understanding how to advance a basic system that they designed and assembled from ground up is very critical for seeing in practice the impact of what is being learned as well as how to implement it in real life/

The results appear to support the previously mentioned teaching methodology, as the complex topics are being recommended for final level of the qualification, and basic for initial level.

The workload should be evenly balanced across all levels in a qualification. The final tallies of the topics, suggests that too many topics are allocated to level 3 while level 2 and 5 are having fewer topics. It’s important to also consider that the time spend for each topic is not the same. It is necessary to take time of each topic to consideration before concluding about the allocation of these topics for each level.

So many of the advanced topics such as software development, Enterprise resource planning, eCommerce, Manufacturing Execution system, Fleet management, Network security have not been included in the consideration of higher levels of learning. Perhaps they should be considered for this qualification in the future as they are becoming more popular in the industry.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available upon request by writing to t.mokgohloa@outlook.com.

10: Acknowledgements

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11: Works Cited

1. **Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica & William L. Hosch.** biography/George-Boole. *www.britannica.com*. [Online] [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] <https://www.britannica.com/biography/George-Boole>.
2. **Wikipedia contributors.** Josef Čapek. *en.wikipedia.org*. [Online] 05 2, 2025. [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Josef_%C4%8Capek.
3. —. Karel Čapek. *en.wikipedia.org*. [Online] Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, 05 2025, 16. [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Karel_%C4%8Capek&oldid=1290715542.
4. —. George Devol. *en.wikipedia.org*. [Online] September 2, 2024. [Cited: May 25, 2025.] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/George_Devol.
5. **Contemporary Controls.** The Extension Volume 4 Issue 2 March-April 2003. *www.ccontrols.com*. [Online] March 2003. [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] <https://www.ccontrols.com/pdf/Extv4n2.pdf>.
6. *Philosophy of Mechatronics.* **Mori, Tetsuro.** 12, 1991, Vol. 57, pp. 1-5. doi.org/10.2493/jjspe.57.2089.
7. **Johannes Kepler University Linz.** The JKU's Milestones. *www.jku.at*. [Online] [Cited: 05 25, 2025.] <https://www.jku.at/en/the-jku/about-us/milestones/#:~:text=1990,academic%20degree%20program%20in%20Mechatronics..>
8. **These are the top 10 job skills of tomorrow – and how long it takes to learn them.** *www.weforum.org*. [Online] 10 21, 2020. [Cited: 05 16, 2024.] <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/10/top-10-work-skills-of-tomorrow-how-long-it-takes-to-learn-them/>.
9. **Mechatronics.** *worldskills.org*. [Online] [Cited: 09 27, 2025.] <https://worldskills.org/skills/id/216/>.

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